

THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT LEARNING STYLE ON STUDENT'S READING COMPREHENSION.

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Abstract This article highlights general information about different learning style on student's reading comprehension and how can they affect their their learning process. The study illustrates comparison of learner centered and teacher centered learning styles.

Key words: learning styles, reading comprehension, teacher centered, learner centered, problem based learning, discovery learning, self-directed learning, cooperative learning, collaborative learning;

A lot of students have probably observed that when they try to learn something new in class, some of them prefer to learn by carefully listening to the teacher who talks about information or perhaps they prefer to read about the information given by teacher, while the rest may be better understood by seeing a direct demonstration from the teacher. It demonstrates that every student responds to new information in the context of learning in a unique way. The trait of a learner that deals with strengths and limitations in taking in and processing knowledge is known as learning style, according to many people. In order to develop such an effective teaching strategy, it is crucial for the teacher to be aware of the students' preferred learning styles. It has been discovered that learning styles, in particular, have an impact on how students absorb and assimilate information. Speaking of information, reading has emerged as one of the most crucial English language learning abilities that many students are still working to acquire, particularly in terms of their reading proficiency. Reading is often considered to be the most important academic skill for language learners to master. Reading comprehension is a useful tool for encouraging people to reflect carefully on the precise purpose of what they

are reading. In truth, many children are fairly proficient readers, but they still struggle to understand what they are reading.

There are numerous ways to categorize, describe, and identify a learning style. In essence, learning style is more concerned with how a student like to learn a subject than it is with what they actually learn. Additionally, everyone has a preferred method for learning new things. While learning, some students may prefer listening to music, others may rely on visual images or presentations, and yet others may do better with hands-on activities. Different learning preferences would cause students to behave differently in how they perceive, engage with, and react to the learning environment.

Teaching- centered learning style

First off all, teacher-led or administrator-centered learning is more frequently used than student-led learning. A student is seen as a learner who ingests knowledge passively, and a teacher's job is to offer that information or to evaluate it in order to make sure that students are getting the appropriate response. The issue is that kids are never given the opportunity to reach their full potential since the emphasis is placed on getting them to score well on exams that are required by the government rather than meeting their needs. This approach is ineffective since students' knowledge is assessed solely by how well they perform on final exams. [Lynch, 1].

Learner -centered learning style.

One of the teaching strategies that teachers employ in the learning process is learner-centered instruction. Learner-centered instruction encompasses a variety of teaching techniques, including: a. small group discussion; b. role playing and simulation; c. case study; d. discovery learning; e. self-directed learning; f. cooperative learning; g. collaborative learning; h. contextual instruction; and i. project-based learning.

Investigative and Problem-Based Learning (j)

With learner-centered instruction, the subjects, exercises, resources, and pace of learning are all decided by the students. This instructional design centers the learning process around the student or learner. Students are given the chance to learn independently and from one another, and the instructor coaches them in the abilities needed to do so successfully. The learner-centered instruction approach uses techniques like assigning open-ended problems and problems that require critical or creative thinking and cannot be solved by simply following text examples, involving students in simulations and role plays, and using self-paced and/or cooperative (team-based) learning. Learner centered instruction that is properly executed can boost motivation to study, knowledge retention, understanding, and positive attitudes about the subject being taught. Learner-centered instruction is a teaching and learning approach that puts an emphasis on supportive connections, each learner's individuality, and the best available research on learning processes in order to encourage holistic student success through engaged their achievement. Some teachers are hesitant to give students the "power" associated with a learner-centered approach because language teaching so frequently assumes a classroom where pupils have very little language skills with which to bargain with the teacher. Such constraint is unnecessary because professors can provide pupils choices even in classes for beginners. All of these initiatives contribute to students' intrinsic motivation by helping them feel like "owners" of their learning.

To conclude, it was determined that learner-centered methods were far more effective than teacher-centered ones and that the former was ineffective. Additionally, teacher-centered strategies cannot be completely abandoned, even when learner-centered approaches yield greater results in terms of learning achievement. They continue to be crucial, particularly for assisting weak students who would struggle in a setting that is solely learner-centered. Once more, this calls for governmental intervention to ensure that instructional techniques are properly balanced based on students' preferences and learning needs.

References:

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2.[http://assessment.uconn.edu/docs/TeacherCenteredVsLearnerCenteredparadigms . pdf.](http://assessment.uconn.edu/docs/TeacherCenteredVsLearnerCenteredparadigms.pdf)